

HORIZON 2020
Research and Innovation action
Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:
A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic

Deliverable 8.4. Quality assurance plan, including
guidelines, best practice examples and project
handbook

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP8
Deliverable no. & title	D8.4. Quality assurance plan, including guidelines, best practice examples and project handbook
Version	V2
Creation Date	08.06.2018
Last change	21.01.2019
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead accepted <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board accepted
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU-Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP- Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO- Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	AWI (partner 1)
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - NPI, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - ULAVAL, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UAF/CFOS, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – AP, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 – CSIC-UTM, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – IOPAN, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – FMI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – DTU-AQUA
Due date	June 2018
Delivery date	January 2019

Deliverable No. 8.4.

Quality assurance plan, including guidelines, best practice examples and project handbook

Abstract

D8.4 defines a set of working procedures, processes and best practice guidelines to ensure quality standards of the project outcomes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to define a consistent set of working procedures, processes and best practice guidelines in order to ensure quality standards of the project outcomes. This document represents a general Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) and project handbook for the ARICE project. Its main aims are

- To manage the interaction between the project partners during the project lifetime;
- To check the progress of the work, on a regular basis;
- To detail how and when the documentation has to be exchanged by the partners and with the European Commission;
- To set editorial standards for project documents and contents;
- To provide documents for distribution to the public using the project's public website available at URL: <http://www.arice.eu>

This document is split into four sections, and includes various annexes:

1. Section I details how the ARICE project is organized and how the relevant consortium bodies will interact during the project;
2. Section II explains how the communication within the Project is organised, and details the publication and communication rules;
3. Section III deals with the technical outputs of the project, including the project reporting;
4. Section IV presents financial statements of the Project

In addition to the present QAP, the project will be guided by major reference documents, which define the objectives, the work program and the operational procedures of the ARICE project:

- the Grant Agreement (GrA) signed by all beneficiaries
- guidance documents provided by the European Commission

The Grant Agreement is available on the intranet of the ARICE website for all project partners: <https://arice.eu/intranet>.

Grant and Consortium Agreements and EC guidance documents can also be found on the EC Participant Portal (EC PP):

<http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/home.html>.

1.1. Facts about ARICE

Acronym/ Contract number: ARICE/ 730965

Title of the Project: ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium: A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research in the Arctic

Starting date / End date: 1st January 2018 until 31st December 2021

Requested EU contribution: €5,996,563.75

Project Coordinator (PC) and Manager (PM): PC: Nicole Biebow: +49 471 4831 1011, nicole.biebow@awi.de

PM: Verónica Willmott: +49 471 4831 2148

Grant Manager: Nancy Lange +49 471 4831 2306

Nancy.Lange@awi.de (in maternity leave until January 2020) and in the meantime substituted by

Svenja Hildebrandt: +49 471 4831 2306, Svenja.Hildebrandt@awi.de

Scientific officer

Agnès Robin: +32 229-93110
agnes.robin@ec.europa.eu

2. PROJECT GOVERNANCE

2.1. General management scheme

The general management structure of ARICE is also presented in part B of the DoA.

2.2. Project bodies description and responsibilities

ARICE is a large project with 14 beneficiaries, two of them non-EU countries (USA and Canada). It therefore requires close cooperation between many institutions and organisations on an international scale. Extensive managerial efforts are required to:

- Ensure that all beneficiaries perform the duties assigned in the GrA Annex I,
- Ensure that all deliverables/milestones/results are handed in in time and that each partner has sufficient resources,
- Detect and help to solve problems, which may arise due to insufficient communication between beneficiaries or for any other reason.

From a Quality Assurance (QA) point of view, it is important that the project management at all levels of the project (strategic, executive and operational), is high skilled and experienced in its duties. The following paragraph describes the responsibilities of each entity.

The responsibilities and composition of the different project governance bodies are described in detail in the ARICE CA and the DoA. The following compilation in table 1 is only a summary of the detailed description in these documents:

Table 1: ARICE governance bodies

Body	Composition/Responsibilities	Decision approval	Planned meetings
Project Coordinator (PC) and Management Team (MT)	<p>The PC of ARICE is Dr. Nicole Biebow, Head of the International Cooperation Department at AWI. She has extensive experience in the management and coordination of large international consortia. The PC will be supported by the Management Team (MT) consisting of four persons based at AWI. The MT is led by Dr. Verónica Willmott (AWI) who has proven experience in project and calls for proposals management. Verónica Willmott will work as a project manager (PM) for ARICE and is tasked by the PC with the day-to day management of the project.</p> <p>She will be assisted by the responsible EU grant manager at AWI (Nancy Lange /Svenja Hildebrandt).</p> <p>The PC supported by the MT will manage the entire Consortium ensuring ARICE’s progress and the achievement of all results envisaged in this proposal. The PC will make all day-to-day decisions and will be the intermediary between the European Commission (EC) and the consortium in all matters. She will be the primary representative of the project in dealings with the EC, policy makers, the public media and other organisations. The PC will task the PM to initiate and organise the production of all reports requested by the EC.</p>	By GA and EB	N/A

Steering Board (SB)	<p>The fundamental role of the Steering Board (SB) is to ensure successful execution of the project. The SB reports to and is accountable to the GA. It will consist of the PC, MT, and WP leaders. Chaired by the PC, the SB will meet at least quarterly, or more often as required by the course of the project. Any member of the SB can call for an extraordinary meeting by a written request.</p> <p>The SB's main responsibilities include the delivery of the project work plan, review of the project progress and the resources status, ensuring the execution of the risk management plans of the project if necessary and ensuring the smooth internal cooperation and relationship between consortium members as well as external project stakeholders.</p> <p>The meetings will be scheduled if possible in conjunction with other meetings and video- and teleconferencing will be used as often as possible to reduce the travel costs.</p>	By GA	Quarterly
General Assembly (GA)	<p>One senior representative from each partner of the project forms the GA, the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. The GA meets at least once a year, over the duration of the project. The GA is chaired by the PC.</p> <p>One permanent representative of the Advisory Board will assist the GA in its decisions but has no own voting rights.</p> <p>Extraordinary meetings of the GA can be convened by a written request from the Steering Board or 1/3 of the members of the GA.</p> <p>The GA's responsibilities include the strategic planning of the project ARICE, the approval of the project deliverables as defined in the Grant Agreement, the approval of periodic and final reports to the EC, the review of the project progress against milestones, and monitoring and implementing any changes necessary in the Consortium Agreement.</p>	Self-decision making organisation	Every year
Scientific Liaison Panel (SLP)	<p>The Scientific Liaison Panel (SLP) is comprised of internationally recognised external experts in the fields of Arctic marine research. The members of the SLP are identified by WP4 and appointed by the GA. One Ethical Advisor has been appointed as member of the Scientific Liaison Panel to oversee any potential ethical issue arising in the evaluation.</p> <p>The role of the SLP is to assist ARICE in the evaluation process and to act as liaison of the ARICE project and the scientific community, maintaining communication and</p>	Self-decision making organisation. Funding decisions to be approved by GA	At least 2 (one per call)

	<p>coordinated actions with research and other marine organisations. The chair of the SLP will be elected from the board and recommended to the GA for approval.</p> <p>Meetings of the SLP will take place to perform a consensus evaluation of the proposals. The Chair of the SLP will take part on the GA meetings and advise on scientific issues.</p>		
Operational Liaison Panel (OLP)	<p>The Operational Liaison Panel (OLP) is comprised of operators of European PRVs and international icebreakers. The members of the OLP are identified by WP1 as the OLP will have a key role on the harmonisation of the Arctic fleet. The members of the OLP are appointed by the GA. The Chair of the OLP will be elected from the panel and recommended to the GA for approval.</p> <p>The operators of the six ARICE PRVs within the OLP will also participate at the logistic evaluation of the proposals submitted to the ARICE calls for proposals.</p>	Self-decision making organisation.	At convened meetings, as needed per WP
Industry Liaison Panel (ILP)	<p>The Industry Liaison Panel (ILP) is comprised of representatives of the Arctic maritime industry. The role of the ILP is to stimulate the connection between science and industry and to give recommendations and support to the strategic vision of ARICE on scientific cooperation with industry. The members of the ILP are nominated by WP2 and appointed by the GA. The chair of the ILP will be elected from the board and recommended to the GA for approval.</p>	Self-decision making organisation	At convened meetings, as needed per WP
Advisory Board (AB)	<p>The Advisory Board (AB) is comprised of international recognised experts in the field of Arctic marine research, representatives of related Polar organisations (e.g. EPB) and relevant stakeholders from industry and politics. The members of the AB are identified by the SB and appointed by the GA. The AB will advise the GA and SB on the enhancement of relationships between Arctic marine industry/Arctic marine research. It will be fundamental in stimulating connection with international partners and organisations as well as with other European initiatives and projects. Its role is also to ensure the transparency of the evaluation process, avoid any conflict of interests and helping ARICE to deal with ethical issues by putting in place the procedures to handle them appropriately.</p> <p>The chair of the AB will be elected from the board members and recommended to the GA for approval. One member of the AB will take place at the SLP proposal evaluation meeting to ensure the transparency of the evaluation process. Meetings of the AB will take place adjacent to the</p>	Self-decision making organisation	

	<p>yearly GA to give the AB members the possibility to follow project progress most closely and to be directly involved in the discussions leading to strategic decisions.</p> <p>The SLP and the ILP will seek the advice of the AB whenever it is necessary for the project course. They can call for extraordinary AB meetings or consult the AB members by video-or teleconferences and electronic communication.</p>		
WP Leaders	<p>While the MT has the overall responsibility for the execution of the work plan, the WP leaders, in conjunction with the appointed task leaders, conduct and manage the project activities. They collaborate closely, using a system of regular internal reporting. At least every third month, task leaders shall summarise their progress towards project deliverables to the WP Leaders, who will review the activity against the work plan and, following discussion with the task leaders, consider if interim targets or measures are required. These reviews will also serve as the basis of more formal reports for the SB, PC, GA and, ultimately, the European Commission.</p>	By SB	When needed
Task Leaders	<p>The task leaders are responsible for the implementation of the individual tasks of the work plan and shall report the task progress to the WP leaders. Task leaders shall establish interactions between individual partners of the task by arranging individual task meetings (video-teleconferenced/web-based virtual meetings, if appropriate). They are also responsible for establishing and maintaining links to other tasks as necessary.</p>	By WP leaders and SB	When needed

Each consortium body shall not deliberate and decide validly unless a quorum of two-third (75%) of its members are present or represented, as specified in the CA (article 6.2.3).

2.3. Work Package and Task management

The management of the WPs and a frequent interaction between WP and task leaders is one of the critical aspects of the success of ARICE. The project is divided into 9 work packages including several tasks which are closely interrelated under a coordinated management scheme (WP8) (see table 2).

Table 2: ARICE Work Packages and Tasks.

Work Package / Task		Leaders
WP1	Towards an Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium	SPRS
Task 1.1	Improving the coordination of European PRVs	SPRS DTU Aqua
Task 1.2	Alignment of national research plans	NPI SPRS
Task 1.3	Towards an International ARICE	SPRS DTU Aqua
Task 1.4	Model for cooperation of the International ARICE	SPRS AWI
WP2	Establishing a regular dialogue with the maritime industry	WOC
Task 2.1	Arctic science community/industry dialogue	WOC
Task 2.2	Identification of joint priorities for Arctic observations	CNR WOC
Task 2.3	Opportunities for key technologies and innovation	WOC
WP3	New generation of polar researchers and professionals	AWI (APECS)
Task 3.1	Online training and resources for multiple audiences	IOPAN AWI (APECS)
Task 3.2	In person/on-site training courses	AWI (APECS) CNR
Task 3.3	Assessment of training activities	AWI (APECS)
WP4	Proposal management and shared evaluation	AWI
Task 4.1	Preparation of call for proposals for ship-time	AWI CSIC-UTM
Task 4.2	Implementation and dissemination of the call for proposals	AP AWI
Task 4.3	Evaluation and selection of proposals	AWI IOPAN
Task 4.4	Allocation of ship-time and post-cruise assessment	CSIC-UTM AWI
WP5	Transnational access to the Arctic Ocean	CSIC-UTM
Task 5.1	ARICE cruises	CSIC-UTM
WP6	Expanding the monitoring and observation capacities in the Arctic Ocean	FMI
Task 6.1	Survey of existing automatic ship based observations	FMI DTU-Aqua
Task 6.2	“Programme of ships and platforms of opportunity”	WOC FMI

Task 6.3	New technological solutions for data collection	FMI CSIC-UTM
WP7	Enhancing virtual and remote access to data	AP
Task 7.1	Data management requirements	AP CSIC-UTM
Task 7.2	Data Management System Design	AP FMI
Task 7.3	3D Virtual Icebreaker	AP NERC-BAS
WP8	Management of the Consortium	AWI
Task 8.1	Contractual and financial management	AWI
Task 8.2	Operational management	AWI
Task 8.3	Communication and Outreach	AP
Task 8.4	Evaluation of the impact of ARICE	CNR
WP9	Ethics requirements	AWI
Task 9.1	Ethics requirements	AWI

More information about the ARICE WPs and tasks can be found in the DoA.

2.4. Meetings

Project meetings necessary for the success of the ARICE project. They are needed to maintain relationship, to promote information exchange, to make agreements and to take major decisions. All beneficiaries have to participate in the GA meetings once a year; since this is the only occasion at which the whole consortium meets. Liaison panels and advisory board representatives are invited to participate in the GA meetings but have no voting rights.

The consortium has decided to have meetings of the ARICE governance bodies with the following minimum frequency:

- General Assembly: once a year
- AB Meetings: once a year in association with the General Assembly
- Steering Board: at least every 3 months, preferably by video- or teleconference
- Work Packages or Tasks: on request

Additional face two face meetings may take place as required but should be limited and video conferences (VC) will be preferably used in order to follow the work in progress. Meetings will be grouped together whenever possible in order to accelerate communication and avoid unnecessary trips and carbon waste.

2.4.1. Official meetings

GA meetings

One meeting every year. The planned meetings for 2018, 2019 and 2020 are the following:

#	Date/Period	Type of Meeting	Meeting Place
1	05/02/2018-07/02/2018	Kick-Off Meeting (KOM) and 1 st General Assembly	Bremerhaven, Germany
2	28-29/03/2019	2 nd General Assembly	Lisbon, Portugal
3	tbd 2020	3 rd General Assembly	tbd
4	tbd 2021	4 th General Assembly	tbd

Executive Board meetings

At least one meeting every 3 months. The next meetings for 2018 have been planned as follows:

#	Date/Period	Meeting place	Special agenda item	Parallel event
1	23/03/2018	VC	Terms of Reference of EB, Call for ship-time proposals, nominations to SLP	1 st GA
2	29/06/2018	VC	WP progress and implementation of Liaison panels	/
3	October 2018	VC	Information on the evaluation of proposals, implementation of the advisory board, pending deliverables	/
4	December 2019/ January 2019	VC	tbd	/

2.4.2. Other meetings

Work Package / Task Meetings

Technical meetings should take place within each WP or even task. The periodicity is not contractually defined, although an average of one meeting per year is intended for each WP usually in association with the ARICE GA.

Attendance at external meetings

Meetings with scientists, industry, Arctic research vessels operators and stakeholders are an important part of the ARICE project since we need their collaboration to improve the access to research vessels in the Arctic Ocean. ARICE will try to implement most of its workshops at international conferences with a large stakeholder representation, to avoid additional travel and to facilitate workshop participation. The ARICE MT will take care that all events are announced early in advance and to a wide audience.

Project partners of ARICE who attend a meeting on behalf of the project are asked to report back to the consortium about the outcomes and major action items derived from this

meeting. Their reports will be made available to the consortium on the internal ARICE website.

A template for reporting is available on the Internal Webpage and in [Annex II.10](#).

2.4.3. Meeting organisation

Official (GA and SB)

GA and SB meetings shall be announced early in advance to allow all project partners to be present or represented. The minimum number of days preceding the meetings are 45 for GA and 14 calendar days for SB.

	Responsible and schedule
Agenda	Produced by the MT. Distributed 21 calendar days prior the meeting to the project partners. Is considered to be final if no comments are received within one week after its distribution.
Actions item list	The actions item list is the summary of the main managerial, administrative and technical decisions taken during the meeting. It is produced by MT. Distributed within two weeks after the meeting to the project partners. Is considered to be final if no comments are received within one week after its distribution.
Minutes	The minutes summarise the discussions and decisions of the GA or EB. They are produced by MT. They will be sent out at the latest 30 days after the meeting. The minutes of the SB are sent to the GA for information. Are considered to be final if no comments are received within two weeks after their distribution.

Other meetings (Work Packages, tasks, etc...)

	Responsible and schedule
Agenda	Produced by the organising partner or WP leader. Distributed two weeks prior the meeting to the involved partners and to the MT. Is considered to be final if no comments are received within 2 days prior its distribution.
Minutes	Produced by the organising partner or WP leader. Distributed within two weeks after the meeting to the involved partners and to the MT. Are considered to be final if no comments are received within two weeks following their distribution.

3. PROJECT COMMUNICATION

3.1. Main communication tools

Various tools will be used to allow and foster internal and external communication (see Table 3).

Table 3: Tools for internal and external communication.

	Used tools	Purpose/comment	Requirements
External	Public website	Public project website (www.arice.eu) for presenting the project and its outcome to the public.	All information and documents on this website are public by nature.
	Social Media	ARICE is active in three social media channels: Twitter and Facebook . Twitter is used to share information with the general public, journalists, scientists and policy makers on ARICE news and events. The Facebook group provide a platform for discussions with group members.	Needs to be administered
	Frostbites	ARICE will create teaching/training materials as a legacy from the summer school.	A dedicated software is needed
Internal	Project internal website	Official document repository: data storage for all documents produced by the project (deliverables, reports, minutes, presentations etc.) or for all documents necessary for the technical, financial and contractual follow-up (Deliverables follow-up, budget breakdown, amendment request etc.) Exchange of project material (templates, official and contractual documents e.g. reports, meeting materials, financial documents, drafts, others) Meeting organization (agenda, minutes, presentations) Working area of the project	Login by institutional account, with password/login Project materials & documentation exchange should be made <u>preferably via the internal website</u>
	E-mail	The internal website contains mailing lists for the different project bodies of ARICE. Emails should only be sent to those mailing lists which are directly related to the subject of the email to avoid a snowball effect. The relation to ARICE shall be made clear in the subject. Large Attachment should preferably be stored on the internal website and not send by email.	Limited exchange of project materials Avoid proliferation

Video Conference (VC)	VC should be used for short meetings in smaller groups when and if possible. This reduces travel costs and accelerates communication.	All required documents must be distributed before the meeting via the collaborative site/email.
------------------------------	--	---

3.2. ARICE external communication

The **ARICE public website** is available at the URL: <http://www.arice.eu>. It is administered by Arctic Portal and AWI has also administration rights. The website is based on Joomla.

It plays an important role in ARICE, as it is the focal tool for communicating and disseminating information generated by the consortium partners. Potential end-users will be scientists, industry, decision-makers, stakeholders and the general public.

In order to facilitate the fast exchange of information among consortium partners and to update the website several templates were developed (see Annex II). Whenever an activity is completed (deliverable; attendance to a meeting; publication...) project beneficiaries are requested to fill them in and submit to the Management Team. With this information the portal will be constantly updated with deliverables, presentations, news, events, etc..

Other important means of communication for ARICE are the **social media channels** Twitter and Facebook. Both channels are used for outreach and engagement roles.

A **e-newsletter** shall be released and distributed by email to inform on news and events. Interested users can register on the public website to receive the ARICE e-newsletter by filling in a registration form, where they can record their e-mails. Users have the possibility to unsubscribe the e-newsletter at any time.

3.3. Internal project website

The internal project website gives access to the whole ARICE consortium through a user login/password.

The login to the ARICE internal website can be found at the following address:

<https://www.arice.eu/intranet>

3.3.1. Structure of the internal website

The intranet of ARICE offers different sections with important documents for the ARICE consortium. Every consortium partner has got a login key and a password to access the internal website.

The intranet is divided in two sections:

1) Documents

The folder “documents” contains:

- The grant agreement
- Mailing lists of project participants
- Presentations and promotional material, and
- Diverse templates

The different sections will be continuously updated during the life-time of the project.

Sicher | https://arice.eu/intranet/documents

Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium
ARICE

An international collaboration strategy for meeting the needs of marine based research in the Arctic

Home About News Outreach Apply for Ship Time Intranet

Intranet / Documents

Documents

Documents (consortium only)
ARICE Grant Agreement (pdf)

ARICE Partners
General partner list (xlsx)
Work Packages - mailing lists (xlsx)

ARICE - Presentations and promotional material
ARICE short info (pptx)
ARICE call for proposals 2018 (pptx)
ARICE poster (pdf)
ARICE brochure (pdf)

ARICE - Templates
Deliverable template (doc)
PPT base for widescreen (pptx)
PPT base for regularsize (pptx)

Home About News Outreach Intranet

Objectives
Partners
Work Packages
Contact information

News
News
Blogs
Articles

Outreach
Media
Calendar
Publications
Links

Intranet
Login
Privacy Policy

EU grant agreement No. 730965

Designed & hosted by Arctic Portal

2) Deliverables

The section “deliverables” shows a table with all the deliverables from the project ARICE in final version as submitted to the EC. Submitted deliverables are downloadable in pdf.

Sicher | https://www.arice.eu/intranet/deliverables

Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium
ARICE

An international collaboration strategy for meeting the needs of marine based research in the Arctic

Home About News Outreach Apply for Ship Time Intranet

Intranet / Deliverables

Deliverables

List of deliverables, sorted by planned delivery date:

Del. No.	Deliverable name	WP#	Short name of lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Planned Delivery date	Actual Delivery Date
D8.1	Project Identity Set (logo, banner, brochure, public website)	WP0	AP	OTHER	PU	February 2018	July 2018
D8.2	Minutes of the Kick off Meeting	WP0	AWI	R	CO	March 2018	May 2018
D8.3	Internal collaborative website	WP0	AWI	DEC	CO	March 2018	July 2018
D8.4	ROD - Requirement No. 1	WP0	AWI	ETHICS	CO	March 2018	May 2018

3.3.2. Access rights

The ARICE internal website is accessible by all ARICE partners but only the following website administrators (Verónica Willmott (AWI), Ævar Karl Karlsson (Arctic Portal) and Fanney Sigrún Ingvadóttir (Arctic Portal) can upload documents and create texts.

3.3.3. Mailing lists

To facilitate internal communication within the project, a general mailing list and dedicated mailing lists for every WP and tasks have been created and are maintained up-to-date by the MT.

The general rules set for e-mails (see above) also apply to mailing lists.

If an update in a list is required, send an email to the MT with the correct e-mail address and targeted group.

3.4. Document and image management

3.4.1. Document confidentiality

All ARICE documents are considered as “**consortium confidential**”, except when they are explicitly mentioned as public documents (PU) in the DoA.

3.4.2. Document templates

All document templates can be found on the internal site in the “Documents” folder from the intranet.

In all document templates, the **Author** is the **lead beneficiary** responsible for the document delivery.

The following templates are available (see Appendix for examples):

For official correspondence:

[An official paper letter \(Word format\): only on request to the MT](#)

For communication:

[A template for publications \(Word format\)](#)

[A template for dissemination activities \(Word format\)](#)

[A template for relevant news \(Word format\)](#)

[A template for news on a Deliverable \(Word format\)](#)

For general purposes:

[General Purpose Document \(Word format\)](#)

[Presentation Template \(Power Point format\)](#)

For meetings:

[Meeting Agenda \(Word format\)](#)

[Meeting Minutes \(Word format\)](#)

For reporting:

[Deliverable Template \(Word format\)](#)

[Milestone Template \(Word format\)](#)

If needed, this list can be updated during the Project life.

3.4.3. Naming conventions and versioning of documents

Recommendations related to the document editing are:

- All documents have to be produced in Microsoft Word format for working versions and Acrobat PDF for final versions;
- Editing language should be set to UK English.

To facilitate their identification, documents produced within the project (Deliverable, Milestone, report, presentation, minutes, paper etc ...) shall integrate the naming conventions defined in [Annex III](#). For the versioning, the documents should be simply implemented as following: 1, 2, 3...

3.5. Publications and dissemination of Project knowledge

Publications and dissemination activities must be reported to the EC in each periodic report and in particular in the final report via dedicated areas in the EC PP. The list of publications and dissemination activities is maintained up-to-date by the Communication leader (Arctic Portal) during the project life using information provided by project's partners (see § 4.2.2.2 and dedicated templates in [Annexes II.2](#) and [II.3](#)).

3.5.1. Types of publications and dissemination activities

Publications or communications may be wholly or largely based on work done for the project and/or contain some material based on work done in the project.

In agreement with the classification described on the EC Participant Portal (PP) (see § 4.2.2.2 and the dedicated template in [Annex II.2](#)), **the following presentation modes are included under the term “publication”**: a peer reviewed publication, a paper in Proceedings of a Conference or a Workshop, an article or a section in an edited book or book series, a Thesis, or a University publication.

The other presentation modes included under the term “Dissemination activities” (see §4.2.2.2 and the dedicated template in [Annex II.3](#)) are: Organisation of a Conference or a Workshop, websites or applications, press releases, flyers, articles published in the popular press, videos, media briefings, presentations, oral presentation to a wider public or to a scientific event, exhibitions, thesis, interviews, films, TV clips or posters.

3.5.2. Rules for publications and dissemination activities, and approval procedure

Usual intellectual ownership and decency rules should be applied. Any proposed publication or communication, regardless of the media (including any plan or model), of the partner's own knowledge is required to be submitted to the other interested partners and to the European Commission. To this end, a brief description and the subject of the proposed publication or communication shall be submitted to the other project partners. The partners shall have the right to object to the publication in accordance with Article 29.1 of the GrA.

For all types of publications and dissemination activities listed in § 3.5.1, beneficiaries must fill in the appropriate templates (available in [Annexes II.2](#) or [II.3](#)) and send them by e-mail to the MT.

For publications and communication to external events in particular, the procedure for approval is the following:

The author(s) send(s) the template for publications (see [Annexe II.2](#)) or the template for dissemination activities (see [Annexe III.2](#)) duly filled in **3 or 6 weeks** prior to the date of publication or submission to the MT.

The author(s) send(s) the publication/communication content to all interested beneficiaries for comments or approval.

When relevant, the author(s) transmit(s) the final version to the MT for storage on the projects internal website, and the MT further to the Communication leader for publication on the ARICE public website.

In addition, it is mandatory for the author(s) to include in publications appropriate acknowledgement to the EC as follows:

These results have been achieved within the ARICE project funded by the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n°730965.

When referring to contributions from other partners, the author(s) is(are) free to phrase the acknowledgement, but must include names, institutes and a reference to the ARICE project such as the Internet website address (<http://www.arice.eu>).

4. PROJECT DELIVERY AND PROJECT REPORTING

The project deliverables are split into 2 categories:

Deliverables and Milestones – see 4.1

Periodic and final reports – see 4.2

Deliverables are the outputs of the tasks within the Work Packages and will be submitted to the EC by the MT via the EC PP.

(<http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/home.html>)

4.1. Deliverables & Milestones

Deliverables and milestones shall be produced according to schedule described in 4.1.1. The following reporting recommendations should be taken into account:

Quality standard (see 4.1.2)

Approval process and storage (see 4.1.3)

Follow-up (see 4.1.4)

4.1.1. Deliverables and Milestones schedule

Deliverables and milestones are to be delivered by the project and assessed at the Due Date (DD) indicated in the DoA. Due Dates (last working day of calendar month) and responsible beneficiaries of deliverables and milestones are respectively listed in the DoA.

4.1.2. Quality standard

The primary responsibility of Work Package (WP) leaders, Task leader and MT is to establish and maintain high standards of technical and professional quality with regard to the objectives set for the project. **All deliverables and milestones in ARICE need to be approved by the Steering Board (SB) prior to uploading them to the EC PP or publishing them.**

All deliverables should be delivered with a summary report and according to the following table and associated guidelines.

Deliverables	Technical specifications and Quality standards
Deliverable report	<p>Shall contain a detailed description of the technical aspects of the deliverable. The template is available on the internal website. See Annex III for the naming convention.</p> <p>Shall be accompanied with an Executive Summary to be provided in the “Template for news on Deliverables” available in Annexe II.3, in order to facilitate its communication to the project’s partners and to public audience via the ARICE website.</p>

- Milestone report Assessment shall be formalised in a milestone assessment report. The template is available on the internal website. See [Annex III](#) for the naming convention.
- The milestone report shall include: The purpose of the milestone, the status, the assessment criteria and the consequences of the milestone result.

The author(s) should comply with general recommendations given for scientific and technical reporting and publishing, and specifically verify that:

- Reference to public sources of information are given;
- Only persons who significantly contributed to the project and manuscript preparation are listed as co-authors;
- The publication do not contain speculative opinions, although it can use scientific evidence to challenge current concepts or propose new ideas that will encourage progress and discussion;
- It is free of evident commercial or private interest, but must neither obscure proper names when they are required.

In the case of critical time delays, and in collaboration with the WP Leaders, measures should be proposed in an effort to avoid potential problems. These measures could be:

1. Re-organisation and re-deployment of the project time plan. All affected partners should be informed about the delay. It is of particular importance to try to minimise resulting project execution delays especially in case of tasks comprising key deliverables of the project;
2. Re-allocation of scientific resources;
3. Although not recommended, request of extension of time to the EC. In this case, the project coordinator presents a detailed report with the difficulties and drawbacks that led to violation of the time constraints and the measures taken during the project in order to overcome these problems as well as the partners responsible for the time delays.

4.1.3. Process for Deliverable/Milestone delivery and storage

The process to ensure a proper delivery of the deliverables and milestones at the Due Date is presented hereafter. The deliverable/milestone approval is based on a 6-step process described as follows:

- One month before the DD, **the MT** sends a reminder to the deliverable/milestone leader, copy to the WP and Task leaders;
- Two weeks before the DD, **the deliverable/milestone leader** sends the deliverable to the WP Lead for validation;
- At the DD, **the deliverable/milestone leader** sends the deliverable/milestone to the MT, copy to the WP leader. It has to be accompanied by the “Template for news on Deliverable” (see annex II); the MT will inform the SB and ask for approval by the SB;

- **The MT** uploads the final and approved version to the intranet site.
- **The MT** submits the approved deliverable to the EC via the EC PP, and informs the WP leader about the submission. For a milestone, the MT updates the Milestone table on the EC PP;
- For public deliverables, **the MT** will take care that the deliverable is published on the project's public website and announced widely.

4.1.4. Deliverables and Milestones follow-up

The follow-up of deliverables and milestones is carried out using updated sheets available on the internal website.

4.2. Periodic and final reporting

4.2.1. Periodic reporting (M18, M36, M48; M60)

This process presented hereafter only deals with technical aspects, please refer to § 5 for financial aspects. Periodic reports have **to be submitted to the EC 60 days after the end of the reporting period**. ARICE spans three reporting periods:

Period 1: M01-M18: 01.01.2018 - 30.06.2019

Period 2: M19-M36: 01.07.2019 - 31.12.2020

Period 3: M37-M48: 01.01.2021 - 31.12.2021

4.2.1.1. Content and structure

A template for the periodic technical reports will be created according to the H2020 online manual, and this template will be uploaded to the internal ARICE website.

The periodic technical report will include an explanation of work carried out, an overview of progress, a publishable summary and a questionnaire. Layout and content of the periodic report must comply with the instructions and guidance notes established by the EC (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/reports/periodic-reports_en.htm). The periodic technical reports are prepared using a dedicated interface available on the EC PP and are structured as follows:

The **explanation of the work carried out** and the **overview of the progress** should show how the action is being implemented and what has already been achieved (as compared to the objectives, milestones and deliverables described in Annex 1 of the DoA). The PC will check if all deliverables due for the period have been submitted. If work planned was not carried out, the beneficiaries must explain why. The **overview of the progress** must also describe how achieved results are exploited and disseminated.

The **publishable summary** must give a brief description of the action, presenting its objectives and the results achieved (in an 'easy to read' way, understandable for a non-specialist audience). The summary must be fit for publication, so that the Commission can publish it on its website right away. If needed, the Commission may make changes to the

summary and publish it (after having given the coordinator the opportunity to comment). The PC must ensure that none of the material submitted for publication includes confidential or 'EU classified' information.

The **questionnaire** must be filled out to provide the Commission with regular up-to-date information for monitoring the action (and ultimately the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme).

The questionnaire consists in structured information on:

- performance indicators (defined in Annex II to the Horizon 2020 Specific Programme)
- information to monitor the implementation of Horizon 2020 on 'cross-cutting issues' (see Annex III to the Specific Programme) and to assess the progress of Horizon 2020 against the objectives defined for the 'societal challenges' (see Article 3 and Annex I to the Specific Programme).

It is designed in a modular way, consisting as much as possible of structured questions, by topic (e.g. publications, patents, innovation, etc.).

4.2.1.2. Approval process for periodic reporting: technical aspects

The following process has been set up to ensure a proper delivery of periodic reports within 60 days after the Due Date. The document is elaborated through a multi-level process where key contributors report according to the template provided by the EC where technical and financial aspects shall be reviewed (see 4.2.1.1).

- One month before the end of the period, **the MT** sends the template for the periodic technical report to the WP leaders for completion of the chapter work progress and achievements per WP during the period;
- 15 days after the end of the period, **WP leaders** transmit their contribution to the MT for consolidation of all WP contributions;
- 30 days after the end of the period, **the MT** starts the preparation to the publishable Summary and transmits the final version to the EB 45 days after the end of the period;
- 55 days after the end of the period, **the SB** validates the final version of the Publishable Summary;
- 60 days after the end of the period, **the MT** submits the periodic report to the EC portal and stores its main components on the internal website.

4.2.2. Final reporting (M60) including dissemination activities and exploitation followed up during the project life

In addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the coordinator must submit the final report within 60 days following the end of the last reporting period.

The final report must include the following:

- (a) a '**final technical report**' with a summary for publication containing:
 - (i) an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
 - (ii) the conclusions on the action, and

- (iii) the socio-economic impact of the action;
- (b) a **'final financial report'** containing
 - (i) a 'final summary financial statement', created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance and
 - (ii) a 'certificate on the financial statements' for each beneficiary, if it requests a total contribution of EUR 325 000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices (see Article 5.2 and Article 6.2, Point A).

Content and structure of these two documents, in particular the final report are described hereafter. Procedures for the preparation and the approval of these two documents will be discussed and approved during the last General Assembly of the project in 2021.

4.2.2.1. Structure of the project final report

The **final technical report** is a summary for publication that should present an overview of the results, their exploitation and dissemination, the action's conclusions and its socio-economic impact.

A template for the final report will be created as soon as the H2020 Online Manual is updated and detailed instructions for the structure of the final report are available. The template will be uploaded to the internal ARICE website. Layout and content of the final report must comply with the instructions and guidance notes established by the EC. It is prepared using the dedicated interface available on the EC PP and is structured as follows:

The **final publishable summary** must cover the whole action. Like the summaries for the periodic reports, the **final summary** must be written in an 'easy to read' way and be understandable for a non-specialist audience. The coordinator must ensure that none of the material submitted for publication includes confidential or 'EU classified' information.

The summary should include:

- an up-to-date link to the action's website
- project logos, diagrams, photographs and videos illustrating the work of the action (if available)

It may also include a list of all beneficiaries, with contact names (if this information should be published).

4.2.2.2. Update of the list of publication and dissemination activities within the EC Participant Portal (EC PP)

It is mandatory to report on publications and dissemination activities via the EC PP through two dedicated links accessible in the EC PP by clicking on the RD icon.

Areas for publications and for dissemination activities are maintained up-to-date in the EC PP by the Communication leader using information provided by the project's beneficiaries in appropriate templates (see § 3.5.2 for the procedure and [Annex II.2 for the template on Publications](#), and [Annex II.3 for the template on Dissemination activities](#)).

- Main page for publications to be filled in using information from the template for publications available in Annexe III.1
- Main page for dissemination activities to be filled in using information from the template for publications available in Annexe III.2

4.2.2.3. Update of the list of exploitable results and project foreground within the EC PP

It is mandatory to report on publications and dissemination activities via the EC PP through two dedicated links accessible in the EC PP by clicking on the RD icon.

4.2.3. Transmission of periodic and final reports

The Coordinator on behalf of the Consortium shall transmit the above documents to the EC via the EC PP.

Reports submitted to the EC, in particular their publishable parts, shall be of a suitable quality to enable direct publication without any additional editing. By submitting the publishable reports to the EC, the MT will also check that they do not include any confidential material.

5. FINANCIAL ASPECTS

5.1. Pre-financing, interim and final payments

As per the ARICE GrA, the project received a **pre-financing of 3,198,167.33€** (representing 53,33% of the 'maximum grant amount' of 5,996,563.75€), including:

- ⇒ An amount of EUR 299,828.19 corresponding to 5% of the maximum grant amount (see Article 5.1), is retained by the Commission from the pre-financing payment and transferred into the 'Guarantee Fund'.
- ⇒ 2,898,339.14 € paid to the Coordinator as a **first advance payment**. Following the payment by the EC, the Coordinator distributed this amount to the project's beneficiaries.

Interim payments reimburse the eligible costs incurred for the implementation of the action during the corresponding reporting periods.

The Commission will pay to the coordinator the amount due as interim payment within 90 days from receiving the periodic report (see Article 20.3), except if Articles 47 or 48 apply.

Payment is subject to the approval of the periodic report. Its approval does not imply recognition of the compliance, authenticity, completeness or correctness of its content.

The total amount of pre-financing and interim payments must not exceed 90% of the maximum grant amount.

The final payment will be made within 30 days after approval by the EC of the final reporting, and the final distribution of the EC financial contribution will be described and transmitted to the EC via the final financial report.

5.2. Cost monitoring and financial reporting via the EC Participant Portal (EC PP)

5.2.1. Eligibility criteria

Eligible costs are defined in Article 6.1 of the GrA (General conditions) and further details are provided in the H2020 Online Manual available on the internal website or on the EC PP (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=160)

Eligible costs have to meet the following criteria:

- Actual : real costs,
- Incurred by the beneficiary,
- Incurred during the duration of the Project (01/01/2018 – 31/12/2021), with the exception of costs relating to final reports and certificates on the financial statements,
- Determined according to the usual accounting and management principles and practices of the beneficiary identifiable and verifiable,
- Used for the sole purpose of achieving the objectives of the Project and its expected results, in a manner consistent with the principles of economy, efficiency and effectiveness,

- Recorded in the accounts of the beneficiary and, in case of any contribution from third parties, recorded in the accounts of the third parties,
- Indicated in the estimated overall budget annexed to the DoA.

5.2.2. Direct and indirects costs

For further details on Direct and Indirect costs, please refer to the EC Financial guide (see § 5.2.1)

The reimbursement of beneficiaries shall be based on their eligible direct and indirect costs.

Direct costs are all those eligible costs which can be attributed directly to the project and are identified by the beneficiary as such, in accordance with its accounting principles and its usual internal rules. The following direct costs may be considered eligible (this list is not exhaustive):

- The cost of personnel assigned to the project;
- Travel and subsistence allowances for staff taking part in the project;
- The costs of consumables and supplies provided they are identifiable and assigned to the project;
- Certificate on the methodology and certificate on the financial statements;
- Conference fees.

Beneficiaries must keep all original support documents for 5 years after the end of the Project, i.e):

The beneficiaries must keep the records and documentation supporting the costs declared ([GrA article 18.1](#)), in particular the following:

(a) for actual costs: adequate records and other supporting documentation to prove the costs declared, such as contracts, subcontracts, invoices and accounting records. In addition, the beneficiaries' usual cost accounting practices and internal control procedures must enable direct reconciliation between the amounts declared, the amounts recorded in their accounts and the amounts stated in the supporting documentation;

- Invoices (hotel, restaurant, purchases, etc.),
- Tickets (train, flight, subway, bus, etc.),
- List of presence signed by the participants to a meeting + programme,
- Other cost justifications.

(b) for unit costs: adequate records and other supporting documentation to prove the number of units declared.

For trans-national access to research infrastructure: This documentation must include records of the names, nationalities, and home institutions of users, as well as the nature and quantity of access provided to them.

Beneficiaries do not need to identify the actual eligible costs covered or to keep or provide supporting documentation (such as accounting statements) to prove the amount per unit.

In addition, for unit costs calculated in accordance with the beneficiary's usual cost accounting practices, the beneficiaries must keep adequate records and documentation to prove that the cost accounting practices used comply with the conditions set out in Article 6.2 AGA.

The beneficiaries, and linked third parties, may submit to the Commission, for approval, a certificate (drawn up in accordance with Annex 6) stating that their usual cost accounting practices comply with these conditions ('certificate on the methodology'). If the certificate is approved, costs declared in line with this methodology will not be challenged subsequently, unless the beneficiaries have concealed information for the purpose of the approval.

In addition, in case of audits, time-sheets for personnel costs justification must be kept for 5 years from the end of the Project:

In addition, for personnel costs (declared as actual costs or on the basis of unit costs), the beneficiaries must keep time records for the number of hours declared. The time records must be in writing and approved by the persons working on the action and their supervisors, at least monthly. In the absence of reliable time records of the hours worked on the action, the EC may accept alternative evidence supporting the number of hours declared, if it considers that it offers an adequate level of assurance.

As an exception, for persons working exclusively on the action, there is no need to keep time records, if the beneficiary signs a declaration confirming that the persons concerned have worked exclusively on the action.

Indirect costs, also called overheads, are all those eligible costs which cannot be identified by the beneficiary as being directly attributed to the project, but which can be identified and justified by its accounting system as being incurred in direct relationship with the eligible direct costs attributed to the project. The indirect cost rate for all beneficiaries within ARICE is 25% of the total direct costs (excl. subcontracting).

5.2.3. Financial Reporting by each beneficiary at M18, M36, M54 and M60

Each beneficiary must declare the costs incurred during the reporting period and must submit them to the EC via the Coordinator within 60 days after the end of the reporting period (see § 4.2.1). This financial statement has to be filled in using a web-based tool accessible from the EC PP, and all financial statement forms and documents shall respect the guidelines provided by the EC (see § 5.2.1). Each beneficiary remains responsible to the EC for its costs claimed even after payment by the EC and even after submission of a Certificate of Financial Statement (CFS).

5.2.3.1. Preparation of the Financial Report by each beneficiary

Costs incurred by the beneficiaries during the reporting periods are declared at the end of each period, i.e. M18, M36 and M48. In order to prepare the cost statement each

beneficiary has to create a draft of the so called Form C using the web-based tool FORCE available in the EC PP.

In the Form C all costs such as Personnel and Travel Costs have to be declared according to the guidelines of the MT, which will be provided as soon as the tool for financial reporting will be available for ARICE in the EC PP. Each beneficiary has to complete a first draft Form C within 30 days after the end of the reporting period. This draft will be evaluated by the MT and if needed, suggestions for corrections will be given to each beneficiary. Only once the MT approves of the Form C the beneficiary has to submit the Form C to their respective FSIGN (Financial Signatory), who will electronically sign and submit the Form C to the PC. Once the Form Cs of all beneficiaries are submitted to the PC, but no later than 60 days after the end of every project period, the PC will submit all Form Cs to the EC.

In the frame of the M36, and M48 cost statement, beneficiaries will also have the possibility to adjust the costs declared in previous periods, i.e. at M18 or M36. Adjustments will be made in dedicated forms (called Adjustment Form C) and specific guidance will be provided by MT at the respective reporting period.

5.2.3.2. Process for cost statement preparation and submission to the EC

The following process is prepared in order to ensure that all individual cost statements will be submitted to the EC by the Coordinator within 60 days after the end of the reporting period:

1. **One month before the end of the reporting period, the MT** sends an email to all beneficiaries to inform them about the upcoming financial reporting, and necessary guidance documents, and to remind of the main steps of the process for the costs statements preparation and submission;
2. **During the first month after the end of the period, each beneficiary** fills in the Draft Form C using the EC PP and informs the MT once the Draft Form C is completed. The Draft Form C, with the explanation on the use of resources, will be validated by the MT who will give suggestions for correction if needed;
3. **One month after the end of period**, providing that the Form C and the use of resources have been validated by the MT, **the beneficiary** is allowed to transmit the Form C for electronic signature to its FSIGN;
4. **At the latest 45 days after the end of the period, the FSIGN** signs the Form C and submits it to the Coordinator;
5. **At the latest 60 days after the end of the period, the MT** submits all Form C to the EC.

5.3. Certificate of Financial Statements (CFS)

Certificate of Financial Statements (CFS) are forms filled in by an external auditor selected by the beneficiary. They contain a number of questions (controls) which the auditor is asked to

answer (check) in verifying the beneficiary accounting and control system or document in relation to the execution of the project.

- CFS are only required when the cumulated EU requested financial contribution exceeds 325,000.00 € at the end of the project with the final financial report;
- CFS must certify all eligible costs of all periods;
- CFS must be submitted according to the templates provided in Annex 5 of the GrA;
- CFS are prepared and certified by independent auditors. Competent public officers could also issue them for public bodies and research organizations.
- CFS has to be scanned by the beneficiary and uploaded in the Form C. They are submitted to the Coordinator and later the EC as Annex to the Form C solely electronically
- The original CFS has to be kept by each beneficiary. No original has to be sent to the Coordinator or the EC.

5.4. Final report on the distribution of the EU financial contribution

The final report on the distribution of the EU financial contribution is a table giving the EU contribution finally allocated to each project beneficiary. This table is filled in by the MT after approval of the EU financial contribution distribution by the project's beneficiaries, and submitted to the EC via the EC portal.

Deliverable No.8.4

Quality assurance plan

ANNEX

ANNEX I Contact details for PC, MT, WP leaders, SB and EEAB

I.1. Project Coordinator (PC) and Management Support Team (MT)

Beneficiary	Name	Position	Email Address
AWI	Nicole Biebow	Coordinator	Nicole.Biebow@awi.de
AWI	Veronica Willmott	Project Manager	Veronica.Willmott@awi.de
	Svenja Hildebrandt	Programme Manager	Svenja.Hildebrandt@awi.de

I.2 Work Package Leaders

Beneficiary	Name	Position	Email Address
SPRS	Nicole Biebow	WP1 Lead	Nicole.Biebow@awi.de
WOC	Christine Valentin	WP2 Lead	christine.valentin@oceancouncil.org
AWI (APECS)	Gerlis Fugmann	WP3 Lead	Gerlis.Fugmann@awi.de
AWI	Veronica Willmott	WP4 Lead	Veronica.willmott@awi.de
CSIC	Miguel Angel Ojeda	WP5 Lead	maojeda@utm.csic.es
FMI	Annu Oikkonen	WP6 Lead	annu.oikkonen@fmi.fi
Arctic Portal	Haldór Johansson	WP7 Lead	halldor@arcticportal.org
AWI	Nicole Biebow	WP8 Lead	Nicole.Biebow@awi.de
AWI	Nicole Biebow	WP9 Lead	Nicole.Biebow@awi.de

I.3 Steering Board

The ARICE Steering Board is comprised by the MT and the WP Leaders.

ANNEX II Templates for communication material

II.1. An official paper letter (Word format)

To

From

date

ARICE

Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium: A strategy for meeting the needs of marine based research in the Arctic Ocean

Project funded by the European Commission

Grant agreement n° 730965

II.2. A template for publications (Word format)

Publication

Type of publication

Title of publication (in English)

Name of the Journal or name of the conference

Planned date of publication

Other relevant information

Abstract

Key words

Author(s)

Full Text

II.3. A template for dissemination activities (Word format)

Dissemination activity

Type of activity

Name of the event (in English)

Date

Venue

Link to event website if available

Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the ARICE project

ARICE Participants at the event and their role

ARICE materials displayed/distributed

Images (Annex images and include credit information)

Other relevant information

II.4. A template for relevant news (Word format)

ARICE News

Title

News text

Source

Website of source OR
annex PDF in case it is
a printed source

II.5. A template for news on a Deliverable (Word format)

ARICE News on a Deliverable

Title of Deliverable

Dissemination level as
per DoW (Consortium
only, Public or
Restricted to a group)

Executive summary of
the deliverable

Responsible institution

Deliverable (Annex the
PDF)

Images/Graphics
(Annex images and
include credit
information)

II.6. Presentation Template (Power Point format)

Template for widescreen (16:9)

Title of presentation

Date of presentation

www.arice.eu

Arctic Research Icebreaker Cons.
ARICE

Grant agreement No 730965

Header – text here

- Main text here or bullets

www.arice.eu

II.7. Meeting Agenda (Word format)

MEETING AGENDA

Conference Date(s)	
Conference Location	
MEETING TITLE Chair:	
Date	
Time	
	Coffee Break
	Lunch
	Coffee Break
Date	
Time	
	Coffee Break
	Lunch
	Coffee Break

II.8. Meeting Minutes (Word format)

HORIZON 2020
Research and Innovation action
Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:
A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic

Minutes of **Conference/Meeting Title**

Minutes of Conference/Meeting Title

Date and Venue:

Rapporteur(s):

Participants:

MEETING AGENDA

Conference Date(s)	
Conference Location	
MEETING TITLE	
Chair:	
Date:	
Time:	
	Coffee break
	Lunch
	Coffee break
Date:	
Time:	
	Coffee break
	Lunch
	Coffee break

1) Session name

Chair:

Time:

Rapporteur:

Attendees:

1.1 Main theme 1

- enter notes

1.2 Main theme 2:

- enter notes

1.3 Main theme 3:

- enter notes

Discussion

- enter notes

Timing and Milestones

#	Title	Lead	Due Date (months)	Means of verification
1				

Action item:

II.9. Meeting Report (Word format)

Meeting Report

Rapporteur:

Meeting details:	
Name of the conference / workshop	
Date and location	
ARICE participant(s)	
Attendees	<i>Please attach list of participants</i>
Agenda	<i>Please attach agenda</i>
Meeting objectives	
Role of ARICE	
Meeting outcome / comments	
Action Items	

PLEASE ATTACH MEETING MINUTES IF AVAILABLE

II.10. Deliverable Template (Word format)

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP 1
Deliverable no. & title	D1.1 Title
Version	Final
Creation Date	31.03.2018
Last change	15.04.2018
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> WP lead accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Executive Board accepted
Dissemination level	<input type="checkbox"/> PU-Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP- Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO- Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	AWI (partner 1)
Contributors	
Due date	30.04.2018
Delivery date	

II.11. Milestone Template (Word format)

Submission of Milestone

Work Package

Milestone no. & title

Version

Creation Date

Last change

Status

- Draft
- WP lead accepted
- Executive Board accepted

Dissemination level

- PU-Public
- PP- Restricted to programme partners
- RE- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium
- CO- Confidential, only for members of the consortium

Lead Beneficiary

AWI (partner 1) (change accordingly)

Contributors

- 1 – AWI, 2 – SPRS, 3 - NPI, 4 - ULAVAL,
- 5 – UAF/CFOS, 6 – AP, 7 – CSIC-UTM, 8 – CNR,
- 9 - WOC, 10 – IOPAN, 11 – FMI, 12 - CNRS,
- 13 – NERC-BAS, 14 – DTU-AQUA

Due date

Delivery date

ARICE

ANNEX III Naming conventions**Deliverables, Milestones and Internal reports**

Document status	File name
Draft/Final	ARICE-WP<wp number>-<Del. or Mil. or Rep. Number>-<DDMMYY>-V<V_Num>

e.g : ARICE-WP1-D1.1-310815-V1

Slideshows/Presentations

Document status	File name
Draft/Final	ARICE -<pres title>-<beneficiary>-<DDMMYY>-V<V_Num>

e.g : ARICE-This is the title of the presentation-AWI-120615-V1

Meeting agenda, minutes and actions list

Document status	File name
Draft/Final	ARICE -WP<wp number>-<Type>-<Date of the meeting>- <Ag. or Min. or List>-<DDMMYY>-V<V_Num>

e.g : ARICE-WP1-EB1-190815-Minutes-190815-V1

Other documents

Document status	File name
Draft/Final	ARICE -<doc title>-<beneficiary>-<DDMMYY>-V<V_Num>